

ML Objectives Perspective

Problem & context

Organizational goals

User goals

Model goals

ML functionality

Leading indicators

Customer expectations

User Experience Perspective

Accountability

Cost

Forcefulness

Frequency

Interactiveness

Value

Prediction visualization

Infrastructure Perspective

Data streaming

Execution engine

Incremental learning

Integration

Safety

Security

Storage

Telemetry

Model Perspective

Algorithms

Explainability

Inference time

Input & Output

Learning time

Maintainability

ML problem

Model performance

Model size

Reproducibility

Data Perspective

Inherent data quality

Accuracy

Bias

Completeness

Consistency

Credibility

Ethics & privacy

Real usage

Baseline

Data operations

Distribution

Quantity

Source

Timeliness